

Matching, weighting, or regression? Evidence from a comprehensive simulation study of Stata treatment effect estimators

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Abstract. Estimating treatment effects with cross-sectional data is one of the most widespread approaches in empirical research. Provided that researchers are able to measure all relevant control variables, it is possible to approximate unbiased (causal) treatment effects. To this end, Stata offers a wide range of standard and user-written commands. Naturally, the question remains which of these methods is most robust for producing unbiased point estimates and valid inference. We address this question by evaluating 14 different commands in a comprehensive simulation study. Using three different settings (unbiased, biased, and incorrect functional form), we analyze a variety of empirically relevant scenarios. Our results indicate that linear (OLS) regression exhibits the lowest bias, the smallest standard errors, and the most accurate coverage in almost all simulation specifications. Entropy balancing and some matching approaches offer advantages when nonlinearities are incorrectly specified. When heterogeneous treatment effects are present, regression adjustment or AIPW approaches deliver the best results. Surprisingly, several methods deviate substantially from the target estimands, even in unbiased “best-case” scenarios.

Keywords: treatment effect, regression, matching, balancing, simulation, causal inference, Stata

1 Introduction

Estimating treatment effects is a common task in almost all fields of empirical research. Accordingly, a large part of statistics is concerned with developing and evaluating methods to achieve this goal. Over the past hundred years, a variety of approaches and techniques have been developed to quantify effects of interest. An overview of the most common approaches is provided by Cunningham (2021):

- Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are usually regarded as the gold standard, especially in clinical research. By randomizing participants into a treatment and a control group, there are no unobserved confounders that can explain treatment

assignment, and group differences reflect causal treatment effects. While the approach is conceptually simple and robust, it can be costly to implement. An even more severe drawback is that some treatments cannot be tested using RCTs due to economic, ethical, or conceptual constraints.

- Longitudinal data analysis can often provide deep insights into phenomena and effects that unfold over longer time periods, particularly individual trajectories. By repeatedly collecting data on the same individuals, fixed-effects approaches can help isolate treatment effects from idiosyncratic differences between subjects. Especially in the social sciences, where treatments often cannot be randomly assigned due to ethical and practical concerns, longitudinal analyses represent one of the most robust sources of evidence. However, because data must be collected over extended periods, costs can be substantial, and additional issues, such as attrition, may bias results.
- Instrumental variable approaches are another robust method for estimating treatment effects and can also be relatively inexpensive. The main limitation of this approach is that finding suitable instruments can be challenging; consequently, it is applicable only to certain topics and research questions.
- Finally, there is the classical approach of statistical control. For the remainder of this paper, we use this term to classify all (cross-sectional) analytical approaches that rely on the identification of confounding factors that can be “controlled for” in order to obtain unbiased treatment effects. As classical frameworks for identifying causal treatment effects demonstrate, provided that these confounding factors are adequately accounted for, the estimation of treatment effects can be as precise and robust as with any of the other approaches discussed above (Pearl 2009).

Given that only cross-sectional data are required, it is not surprising that the classical approach of accounting for potential confounding is among the most widespread empirical research tasks. Typically, after reviewing prior findings and developing appropriate theoretical frameworks, directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) are used to identify the factors that need to be accounted for (Digitale et al. 2022). After data collection, an appropriate statistical approach can then be applied to adjust for confounders and estimate an unbiased treatment effect. This paper focuses on such approaches. As readers are likely aware, the popularity of this general strategy has led to the development of a large number of statistical methods that explicitly address the problem of confounding in cross-sectional analyses. These methods may be based on, for example, regression, matching, or weighting techniques. Regardless of the specific approach or mechanism, they all share a common objective: to make observations in the treatment and control groups sufficiently similar so as to approximate a randomized controlled trial in which potentially confounding factors no longer predict treatment assignment.

While the availability of a wide range of approaches is generally desirable—providing researchers with multiple options to choose from—this abundance can also pose a substantial challenge, as method choice may materially affect empirical findings. Although many approaches have been developed, often grounded in sophisticated theoretical and

statistical frameworks, their real-world performance may fall short of expectations. Because empirical data can exhibit an almost unlimited variety of constellations—depending on research questions, variables, settings, and many other factors—selecting the “best” method is a difficult task. In practice, this choice is often guided less by formal statistical criteria than by convenience and convention. The family of regression-based approaches, despite their relatively simple structure, has enjoyed sustained popularity over recent decades, largely due to their familiarity and flexibility. Because these methods can easily accommodate a wide range of distributions and covariates, they are widely used across many research fields. At the same time, more sophisticated statistical approaches have been developed that appear, at least in theory, to offer advantages over regression methods that were often introduced several decades ago.

The objective of this paper is to empirically investigate which cross-sectional control approaches available in Stata perform best. As noted above, given the vast range of possible data-generating processes, such an analysis can only cover a limited set of scenarios. Nevertheless, the results may still provide useful guidance for researchers when selecting an appropriate method. We begin by providing an overview of the most commonly used methods in empirical research and their popularity over time. We then conduct a comprehensive simulation study evaluating 14 different Stata commands for estimating treatment effects in a cross-sectional setting with continuous and approximately normally distributed outcome variables.

2 Popularity of controlling approaches

By examining two major databases that contain hundreds of thousands of published and peer-reviewed research papers, we aim to assess general interest in various approaches used to estimate treatment effects through statistical control. For this purpose, we selected PubMed.org, which primarily indexes clinical research, and Web of Science (WOS, Clarivate).¹ To avoid double counting clinical research findings when using WOS, we restricted the scope of this database accordingly.² We classified the methods into seven distinct approaches: linear (OLS) regression, entropy balancing (EB), propensity score matching and related matching approaches (PSM), Mahalanobis distance matching (MD), (augmented) inverse probability weighting (IPW), coarsened exact matching (CEM), and regression adjustment approaches (RA). The results are shown in Figure 1 (years were selected to ensure that a variety of approaches are represented).

As the results indicate, trends are upward for almost all methods. While PSM has been the most popular approach from the outset, interest in this method continues to grow over time. Because some approaches were introduced much earlier than others, it is unsurprising that more established methods currently exhibit higher levels of popularity, while newer approaches are still catching up. The largest increases over the observation

1. Special thanks to Paul-Richard Mansfeld for supporting the review of the databases.

2. Excluded are the STEM fields and medicine, leaving social sciences, psychology, business, and related fields.

Figure 1: Absolute number of research findings in two large online databases by year and method. Note the logarithmic scaling of the y-axis.

period are observed for entropy balancing (+50%), propensity score matching (+24%), and coarsened exact matching (+24%).

For our purposes, two findings from this overview are particularly important. First, interest in statistical approaches based on controlling for confounding has increased over time. Despite the well-founded argument that research designs such as randomized controlled trials or longitudinal analyses can enhance causal credibility, many studies must rely on cross-sectional data due to practical constraints. Second, interest appears to be growing across all methods. This is an important observation, as it suggests that no clear gold standard has yet emerged. If one method were demonstrably superior, one would expect its use to increase disproportionately while others stagnated or declined. Evidently, this is not the case, and there is no consensus regarding which method performs best. Of course, this does not imply that all methods considered here are of equal quality; rather, it suggests that any existing differences in performance do not readily translate into differences in popularity.

3 Simulation study

3.1 Stata commands and specifications

In total, we test 14 different approaches to estimating treatment effects in Stata. The first method is a linear (OLS) regression, implemented using `regress`.³

The second family of Stata commands is provided by the `teffects` suite.⁴ We evaluate augmented inverse probability weighting (`aipw`), inverse probability weighting (`ipw`), inverse probability weighting regression adjustment (`ipwra`), nearest-neighbor matching (`nnmatch`), propensity score matching (`psmatch`), and regression adjustment (`ra`). This suite encompasses a wide range of commonly used methods, and the syntax is largely consistent across commands. All remaining commands considered are community-contributed and are not part of official Stata releases.

The first of these modules is `kmatch` by Ben Jann.⁵ While some approaches are also available in official Stata commands (such as propensity score matching), others are unique, such as entropy balancing. The full set of subcommands includes entropy balancing, (coarsened) exact matching, propensity score matching (with kernel matching), multivariate distance matching, inverse probability weighting, and regression adjustment. Finally, Śłoczyński, Uysal, and Wooldridge show that, provided the propensity score is estimated in a particular way, IPW, AIPW, and IPWRA estimators yield identical results (Śłoczyński et al. 2025). They introduce the Stata module `teffects2`. Because its three subcommands produce identical estimates, we evaluate only the computationally fastest option (IPW).

In the simulation, unless otherwise specified, all options are left at their default values. Several exceptions apply. First, `kmatch eb` (entropy balancing via `kmatch`) attempts to balance means, standard deviations, skewness, and covariances whenever possible. If estimation fails, the complexity of the balancing constraints is reduced sequentially in the following order: covariances, skewness, and standard deviations. Balancing as many moments as possible appears important for fully exploiting the entropy-balancing strategy. Second, exact matching uses Scott's rule to coarsen continuous covariates.⁶ This approach is well suited to normally distributed variables and is also implemented in other software, such as Microsoft Excel. Third, all subcommands in the `kmatch` family restrict estimation to the region of common support when computing treatment effects; by doing so, observations with extreme propensity scores that could potentially bias results are excluded. As many of Stata's `teffects` command also enforces this, the results should be comparable. Note that some subcommands, such as exact matching, do not support this restriction. Fourth, Stata's nearest-neighbor and propensity score matching commands match on exactly one neighbor and apply

3. Related methods include robust regression (`rreg`) and quantile (or median) regression (`qreg`). Our tests show that results based on these commands are quite similar and only marginally worse than those obtained with `regress`; hence, they are not reported. In specific settings (e.g., non-normal outcome distributions or the presence of extreme outliers), these methods may offer advantages.

4. Available since Stata 13.

5. <https://github.com/benjann/kmatch>

6. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Histogram#Scott's_normal_reference_rule

the bias correction for the specified number of covariates (*biasadj(varlist)*). Fifth and finally, all Stata commands that allow the specification of a treatment model use a *logit* specification.

3.2 Simulation specification

The general simulation setup is as follows. At first, a set of (correlated) confounders is generated as a multivariate normal vector:

$$\mathbf{C}_i = (C_{i1}, \dots, C_{ip})^\top$$

Next, the linear confounder index is defined as

$$\eta_i = \sum_{j=1}^p C_{ij}$$

Treatment assignment is generated from a noisy logistic index model. Let

$$D_i = 1\{\text{logit}^{-1}(\eta_i + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_T^2)) < \pi\}$$

Where π controls the marginal treatment prevalence and 1 being the indicator function. The noise variance σ_T^2 is adaptively increased until the coefficient of determination from a linear regression of D_i on all confounders satisfies

$$R^2(D_i | \mathbf{C}_i) \leq 0.35$$

This is done so that the explanatory power of the confounding variables is not too large; otherwise the analyses models might fail to compute any result at all as finding suitable control cases becomes (virtually) impossible. Finally, the betas of the confounders are randomly assigned as such:

$$S = \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_j$$

with

$$\alpha_j \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$$

The empirical treatment effect is defined relative to the total confounder influence ($\tau = \text{effect} \times S$). Finally, the treatment assignment model is defined as:

$$Y_i = \tau D_i + \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_j C_{ij} + \mathcal{N}(0, 0.88^2)$$

In total, four different simulation studies are conducted. All share a similar overall design. The dependent variable is continuous and approximately normally distributed and depends on a binary treatment variable and one or more confounding variables. These confounders affect both treatment assignment and the outcome. Within this general framework, several factors are varied systematically to generate a wide range of data constellations.

- The number of observations is either 500, 1500, or 5000, corresponding to small, intermediate, and large samples.
- The mean of the binary treatment variable (π) is either 0.50, 0.25, or 0.15. Because

the mean reflects the share of ones in this binary variable, this factor determines how balanced the sample is with respect to treatment status; the treatment group is either balanced or relatively small.

- The number of confounders (p) is either 1, 3, or 7.⁷
- The average correlation among the confounders is either 0, 0.10, or 0.20.
- The true treatment effect (τ) is either 0, 0.15, 0.50, or 1. The magnitude of the treatment effect is defined relative to the total regression weights of the confounders. For example, a value of 0.50 indicates that the treatment effect equals 50% of the total confounder effect on the outcome variable, whereas a value of 0 indicates that no true treatment effect is present.

Based on these general specifications, four main settings are designed. The first corresponds to a best-case scenario in which no bias is present. In this setting, the estimation commands include the treatment variable and all confounders that are part of the data-generating process; consequently, the resulting estimates should be unbiased on average. However, this setup is rather unrealistic, as in applied research some confounding influences are likely to remain unobserved even when many relevant variables are measured. Therefore, in the second setting, one of the confounders is randomly selected and omitted from the estimation command. As a result, the corresponding estimates are expected to be biased to some degree.

The third specification builds on the second and focuses on nonlinear effects. In practice, researchers often do not explicitly consider the functional form of the relationship between variables and include only linear effects of confounders. This implicitly assumes that higher values of a confounder linearly increase or decrease the probability of treatment assignment. If the true relationship is instead nonlinear—for example, quadratic—the resulting estimates will be biased. To simulate this situation, in the third setting one of the confounding variables is randomly selected and its squared term is allowed to affect both treatment assignment and the outcome. However, this squared term is not included in the estimation command, which again leads to biased results on average. Lastly, in the fourth specification, heterogeneous treatment effects are introduced. While in this specification, no biases or nonlinear effects are present, the strength of the treatment depends on a confounder. Technically, this effect is produced by randomly selecting one of the confounders and generating the interaction term between this confounder and the treatment variable, which is then included in the outcome generating process. In technical terms, due to this specification, the ATT and ATC will differ, on average.

In the first setting, every estimator should be able to recover the true treatment effect, as no confounders are omitted. In the second and third settings, estimates are necessarily biased to some extent. Nevertheless, when confounding variables are correlated—either by design or through the inclusion of nonlinear effects—a well-performing method should be able to reduce bias by exploiting the additional information, at least

7. For the setting with the biased estimator, the number of confounders is either 2, 5, or 7.

partially. In the fourth specification, the results are technically not biased as the average treatment effect is still the same. However, some methods are expected to give somewhat biased results in this setting (such as the linear regression).

For each of the four settings, the total number of simulations is determined by forming all possible combinations of the specifications, resulting in 324 simulations per setting. For each simulation, 300 repetitions are conducted to ensure a sufficiently large amount of information.⁸ Although there is no theoretical justification for this specific number, extensive testing has shown that it is more than sufficient to produce stable and highly precise results. After completing all simulations, three main aspects are evaluated. First, because the data-generating process is known, the true and unbiased target effect is available. The primary statistic of interest is the absolute difference between this target effect and the estimated effect produced by each method. Second, we examine the standard error associated with the point estimate. Based on these and related statistics (such as confidence interval bounds), further analyses are conducted.

To analyze these outcomes, linear (OLS) regression models are estimated. Because each method is applied to identical data, clustered standard errors by repetition are specified to ensure valid comparisons. Rather than reporting regression coefficients, we present marginal effects to facilitate interpretation.⁹ To avoid distortions due to extreme outliers, observations with exceptionally large deviations are excluded. Specifically, for each simulation setting, values above the 99th percentile of the absolute difference between the target and estimated effects are removed (trimming). All analyses are conducted in Stata 18.0 using `parallel` (Vega Yon and Quistorff 2019), and various visualizations are produced with `coefplot` (Jann 2014).

3.3 What is your estimand?

Recent discussions in sociological research have highlighted that many empirical studies neither clearly define their theoretical nor their empirical estimand, which can lead to results being misinterpreted or failing to address the underlying research questions (Lundberg et al. 2021). For this study, the empirical estimand is of particular interest. All methods considered—except linear regression—report the Average Treatment Effect (ATE).¹⁰ While reporting the ATE as an empirical estimand is, in principle, appropriate, depending on the specific research objective, recent work has shown that regression coefficients and ATEs are not necessarily comparable, which may lead to confusion. Depending on the data-generating process, these two empirical estimands can differ substantially, raising the question of whether it is meaningful to compare results from linear regression with those obtained from other commands. In applied research, regression coefficients can be transformed into ATEs using a relatively straightforward procedure, thereby allowing a valid comparison. In the simulation specifications one,

8. The simulation specification with heterogeneous treatment effects is currently conducted with 270 repetitions and will be updated in the future.

9. Because all commands are tested on exactly the same data, the ceteris paribus condition always holds; hence, arithmetic means would technically suffice.

10. Most commands also allow users to report the ATT or the ATC.

two, and three, all effects are homogeneous, meaning that regression coefficients and ATEs are expected to be identical by design. In the fourth specification, when heterogeneous treatment effects are specified, the regression coefficients are not transformed so one can judge the amount of bias when using this method.

3.4 Results

In this section, we provide and explain the simulation results (keep in mind that extreme outliers have been removed from all analyses, as explained above). A standardized simulation analysis is possible with the user-written command `simsum` (White 2010). We provide this output in the appendix (Table 2). Overall convergence statistics for the point estimate are reported in Table 1. It outlines that most commands produce a valid result in almost all settings. There are two notable exceptions. `kmatch em` fails to produce a result very often in general (only about 67% in comparison to `regress`) and `teffects2 ipw` has problems when the functional form is specified incorrectly (98.5%, compared to `regress`). What this table shows is that the number of valid results differs by command, as some commands could not produce a valid point estimate or standard error. Whenever one of these two relevant statistics is missing, we also set the other statistic to missing as these results are probably unreliable, in general. We decided to not form a common sample but analyse all results as-is. Otherwise, due to the extremely large number of missing values from `kmatch em`, the sample would be drastically altered. Our tests have shown that `kmatch em` fails to produce results when the number of confounders is large, which basically rules out the application of this command for settings with a high number of control variables.

Table 1: Convergence statistics by method and simulation specification

Method	Unbiased	Biased	Incorr. funct. form	Heterog.	Total
reg	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
km_eb	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
km_em	64,793	64,959	64,794	64,798	259,342
km_ps	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
km_md	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
km_ipw	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
km_ra	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
aipw	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
ipw	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
ipwra	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
nnmatch	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
psmatch	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
ra	96,228	96,228	95,930	96,228	384,614
t2_ipw	96,167	96,219	94,497	96,162	383,045
Total	1,315,696	1,315,914	1,310,449	1,315,696	5,257,755

Note: reported are the number of valid results. The only command that displays serious issues is `kmatch em`, as it has problems handling multiple control variables.

Unbiased simulation setting

In the first setting, all confounding variables are included in the estimation commands; consequently, all methods should yield unbiased results on average. The first outcome of interest is the absolute difference between the target value and the point estimate. The second outcome is the standard error of the point estimate. Results are reported in Figure 2. For all subsequent figures, the order of commands is identical: `regress`, `kmatch eb`, `kmatch em`, `kmatch ps`, `kmatch ipw`, `kmatch ra`, `teffects aipw`, `teffects ipw`, `teffects ipwra`, `teffects nnmatch`, `teffects psmatch`, `teffects ra`, `teffects2 ipw`.

Figure 2: Absolute difference between target value and computed point estimate (left panel) and the corresponding standard error (right panel), $N = 1,315,696$. Confidence intervals are not shown because they are very short. Results for `kmatch em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

As shown in Figure 2, `regress` yields the smallest absolute difference from the target value, with a median of 0.048. All other commands exceed this value, although most are relatively close. The only methods that exhibit substantial deviations from the target on average are `teffects ipw`, `kmatch em`, and `kmatch md`.¹¹ The particularly poor performance of the latter may be attributable to the large number of tuning options available for the algorithm; in particular, the `metric()` option may be crucial for obtaining sensible results (the default metric is Mahalanobis distance). The same goes for the

11. While the results for `kmatch em` seem fine, the number of data points is much lower since the program often did not converge and failed to produce any result at all, see Table A1.

coarsened exact matching, which offers a variety of algorithms. However, while some algorithms might be better than others, as Scott’s formula has been widely implemented in other software, the overall very poor performance cannot easily be explained.

With respect to standard errors, `regress` again produces the smallest values on average. Here, however, there is greater heterogeneity across methods. Some commands that show relatively small deviations from the target exhibit substantially larger standard errors, such as `kmatch eb` and `teffects psmatch`. In general, the absolute magnitude of the standard error is less informative than the resulting coverage. Coverage refers to the probability that a confidence interval contains the true parameter value. When the nominal significance level is set to 5% (yielding 95% confidence intervals), coverage should equal 95%. Because the true parameter is known in all simulations, we can compute the empirical coverage for each method. These results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Coverage for the unbiased simulation setting, $N = 1,347,192$. Confidence intervals are not shown because they are very short. Target coverage is 95%. Results for `kmatch em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

Most commands exhibit coverage rates that are close to the nominal value of 95%. As in the previous results, `regress` is closest to the target. Several methods display coverage rates exceeding 98% (`kmatch eb`, `kmatch ps`, and `kmatch ipw`), indicating conservative behavior, as higher coverage makes rejection of the null hypothesis less likely. By contrast, some commands are overly liberal. While `teffects psmatch` and `teffects2 ipw` achieve coverage rates close to 90%, `kmatch md` and `teffects ipw`

deviate substantially from the nominal level.

To gain further insight, we conduct additional analyses in which the defining factors of the simulation design are used as explanatory variables. These factors are interacted with the estimation commands to assess whether certain methods respond differently to specific settings. Because each command may exhibit varying performance across specifications, we compute the coefficient of variation for each method. This measure quantifies the extent to which a command responds to changes in the simulation design. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Coefficient of variation for each command by changes in the simulation specification. Larger values indicate greater “sensitivity”, $N = 1,315,696$. Treatment mean indicates whether the treatment variable is balanced or not. Results for `kmatch em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

The interpretation of these results is as follows. With respect to the absolute difference from the target value, linear regression shows substantial sensitivity to changes in sample size, indicating that `regress` responds noticeably to variation in sample size. This is a rather general finding and applies to almost all methods. However, when the remaining three parameters vary, changes in the results for `regress` are minimal, as indicated by coefficients of variation close to zero. For other methods, this pattern differs markedly. For example, `kmatch em` is quite sensitive to the number of confounders included.

In summary, absolute deviations from the target increase with smaller sample sizes, a larger number of confounders, more imbalanced treatment assignment, and higher

correlations among confounders. Nevertheless, as Figure 4 illustrates, some commands show little to no response to these changes in the simulation specification.

Finally, we examine the statistical power of each command. Statistical power is defined as the probability of detecting a treatment effect when such an effect exists in the data-generating process. Because the true treatment effects are known and take values of 0, 0.15, 0.50, or 1.0, we use the latter three specifications to assess power. The results are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Statistical power analysis, $N_{\min} = 336,532$. 95% confidence intervals included. Results for `kmatch em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

When the effect size is relatively small, at only 15% of the magnitude of the total confounder effect, most methods achieve power levels of around 80%. Only `kmatch md`, `teffects ipw`, and `teffects psmatch` perform noticeably worse. As expected, statistical power increases with larger effect sizes, and differences between commands become negligible. Overall, `regress` exhibits the strongest performance across the considered specifications.

Omitted variable bias

The second simulation introduces omitted variable bias. In this setting, one of the confounders is randomly selected and excluded from the list of control variables. As a consequence, treatment effect estimates are biased. All other aspects of the simulation design remain unchanged. The results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Simulation results in the presence of omitted variable bias, $N = 1,347,183$. Results for `kmmatch em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

As expected, absolute differences between the target effect and the estimated point estimates are substantially larger in this setting. The smallest deviations are observed for `kmmatch ipw` and `regress`, with both commands yielding very similar results. Notably, only the `kmmatch` implementation of inverse probability weighting achieves this level of performance; the corresponding `teffects` implementation performs considerably worse. Although `kmmatch ipw` offers a slight advantage in terms of bias, its standard errors are much larger than those produced by `regress`. One might expect the magnitude of the bias to decrease as the intercorrelation among confounders increases, as additional information becomes available. This hypothesis is examined in Figure 7.

As shown in Figure 7, nearly all commands benefit similarly from higher intercorrelations among confounders, with the notable exception of `kmmatch md`.

Incorrect functional form

The third simulation setting introduces a nonlinear functional form. For this purpose, one of the confounding variables is randomly selected and its squared term is generated. This term is specified to affect both treatment assignment and the outcome variable, but it is not included as a control variable in the estimation command. Consequently, the estimates are again biased, this time because only the linear component of the confounder is accounted for, while the nonlinear influence is omitted. This setting

Figure 7: Absolute difference from the target value in the biased simulation setting by degree of intercorrelation among confounders (average correlation equal to 0, 0.10, or 0.20), $N = 1,315,914$. Results for `kmatach em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

simulates a model misspecification scenario in which all relevant variables are observed, but the researcher incorrectly assumes linear effects only. The results are shown in Figure 8.

In this setting, `kmatach eb` exhibits a clear advantage, with comparatively small deviations from the target value. Keep in mind that the result from `kmatach em` should not be interpreted, since it failed to converge in a large number of simulations at all. The second-best performance is achieved by `teffects nnmatch`, followed by `kmatach ps`. Nevertheless, a substantial number of commands produce deviations that are larger than those obtained from the comparatively simple OLS approach. Moreover, although the entropy-balancing approach yields the smallest bias, it is also associated with the largest standard errors, which are almost twice as large as those from the OLS regression.

Heterogeneous treatment effects

In the fourth and final simulation specification, heterogeneous treatment effects are tested. It should be underscored that in this setup, the size of the treatment group is relevant. Classical regression coefficients are biased as long as sizes are unequal, with larger imbalances resulting in larger biases (2023). Consequently, we stratify the analyses by relative size of the treatment group (either 50, 25, or 15%). Results are

Figure 8: Simulation results in the presence of model specification error (failure to account for a quadratic confounder effect), $N = 1,310,449$. Results for `kmatch em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

presented in

While the raw regression coefficients are fine as long as the relative size of the treatment group is balanced, there is bias present as soon as the groups have an unequal size. This demonstrates that regression coefficients are biased in the presence of heterogeneous treatment effects and unequal treatment group sizes. While the general trend of larger biases with more unequal sizes is present in all methods, the size of the bias is smaller in most other approaches. The best results are given by the regression adjustment approaches, which also have rather small standard errors. It is rather concerning that many methods display very large standard errors, even when their bias is rather fine. One outlier seems to be `teffects ipw` approach, which has biases even larger than `regress`, despite computing the ATE. To summarize, methods do clearly differ also in the presence of heterogeneous treatment effects and users should select a method with care. For additional insight, especially regarding coverage rates, refer to the appendix.

4 Discussion

The simulation study, which tests 14 different Stata commands for estimating (causal) treatment effects using cross-sectional data, reveals several noteworthy results. We be-

Figure 9: Simulation results in the presence of heterogeneous treatment effects (otherwise, no biases or nonlinear effects are present), stratified by relative size of the treatment group. $N = 1,315,696$. Results for `kmatch em` should be interpreted with extreme caution, as the number of valid simulation results is much lower!

gin by considering the best-case scenario, in which all confounders are observed and included in the estimation. In this setting, no method should produce biased results. While this expectation is largely met, there are three notable exceptions. The first is `kmatch em`, which implements coarsened exact matching. While the general results in the figures seem fine, the appendix Table clearly indicates that this method very often fails to converge, producing not results at all. This is troubling and potentially related to the number of confounders. As soon as many control variables need to be coarsened, the algorithm fails rather often. Since all covariates are continuous and approximately normally distributed, the coarsening is required to find matches. Apparently, while coarsening makes sense theoretically to handle continuous variables with a very large number of distinct values that prevent a perfect match, this step introduces bias and renders the results problematic. The second is `kmatch md`, which implements multivariate distance matching. For this command, deviations between the target value and the estimates are also substantial. This may be attributable to the complexity of the matching procedure, as the default settings may not be well suited to the specific simulation design. Moreover, some users may already view this command with caution, as it is a user-contributed rather than an official Stata command. In contrast, the comparatively poor performance of `teffects ipw` is more concerning, as this command is part of official Stata and offers relatively few tuning options for the user. One potentially relevant choice is the specification of the treatment model, for which *logit*, *probit*, and *hetpro*

bit are available (*logit* is the default and was used throughout the simulations). Why **teffects ipw** exhibits such large deviations in this setting remains unclear, and users may therefore wish to exercise caution when applying this method. Overall, the clear winner in terms of bias is the classical linear regression. This result is perhaps unsurprising, as the simplest and most established approach may be sufficient in a best-case scenario where no complications arise.

With respect to inference, **regress** also performs best. A more troubling finding is that, although many commands yield relatively unbiased point estimates, their standard errors are often much larger than necessary. As a result, inference is less precise, making it more difficult to accurately determine the magnitude of treatment effects. For example, although **kmatch eb** produces reasonably accurate point estimates, its standard errors are almost twice as large as those from **regress**. This does not imply that inference is generally invalid, as coverage rates indicate that most methods achieve values close to the nominal level. However, some commands, such as **teffects nnmatch**, deviate by roughly five percentage points.¹²

In summary, there is little reason not to use the most basic approach—linear regression as implemented in **regress**. This method yields the lowest bias and standard errors, achieves near-perfect coverage, and delivers the highest statistical power. Additional analyses show that **regress** responds primarily to changes in sample size (as expected) but is remarkably stable with respect to other design features, such as the number of confounders or imbalanced treatment assignment. Although not examined in this simulation, a further advantage of **regress** is its ability to accommodate multivalued treatments, which are not supported by many of the other commands considered.

Best-case scenarios, however, are rare in applied research. Omitted variable bias and model misspecification are common challenges. To address the former, the second simulation omits one confounding variable from the estimation process, reflecting situations in which researchers are unable to measure a confounder or are unaware of its relevance. As expected, all methods perform substantially worse in this setting, as no estimator can recover information that is not present in the data. While most commands exhibit similar levels of bias, **teffects ipw** and **kmatch md** again perform worse than average. Standard errors also vary considerably. When omitted variable bias is anticipated, researchers may therefore prefer **kmatch ipw** or **regress**.

The third simulation introduces model misspecification. In this case, all relevant confounders are observed, but the researcher is unaware of the nonlinear (quadratic) influence of one confounder. As discussed earlier, this situation can lead to misleading conclusions. The straightforward remedy is to include a higher-order term for the relevant variable. However, when theory does not suggest such nonlinearity, many researchers may rely on a linear specification without adequately testing for nonlinear

12. Users should note that **teffects nnmatch** and **psmatch** were implemented using a single match per treated observation, which is generally not recommended but is the Stata default. While such strict matching may benefit point estimates, it is often suboptimal for inference. The literature offers various recommendations for selecting this parameter; see <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2962254/>.

effects. The question, then, is whether the estimation command itself can mitigate this problem. Although no method yields unbiased estimates in this setting, some perform better than others. The smallest bias is observed for entropy balancing. This result is in line with a previous study that compared various Stata methods to achieve covariate balancing (Bittmann et al. 2021), where balancing and coarsened exact matching performed very well. As noted previously, effective use of this approach requires balancing as many moments as possible—not only means, but also standard deviations, and, where feasible, skewness and covariances. Increasing model complexity may lead to convergence problems, particularly in smaller samples. Users should therefore be aware that careful tuning is necessary to fully exploit entropy balancing as implemented in `kmatch eb` (as of Stata 19, no official Stata command implements this method).

The second-best performer in this setting is nearest-neighbor matching via `teffects nnmatch`. While this approach outperforms many others, it requires users to choose the number of neighbors, which involves additional judgment and tuning. Kernel matching and inverse probability weighting as implemented in `kmatch ps` and `kmatch ipw` perform slightly worse but still better than the fifth-ranked option, `regress`. Ultimately, the most effective way to avoid such problems is to correctly specify the estimation model. This requires strong theoretical guidance and careful descriptive analysis to understand relationships among variables. There is no simple procedure that can fully substitute for these steps. A somewhat simpler diagnostic test is proposed by Miller, who is generally skeptical of matching methods.¹³

In the last simulation specification, heterogeneous treatment effects are introduced. As soon as the size of treatment and control group are unequal, this leads to biased regression coefficients, which we also see in the results. This rather simple example underscores that regression coefficients are not always the best choice. However, this does not automatically mean that all other methods, which report ATEs, perform better. Some methods, such as `teffects ipw`, perform even worse than `regress`. This is alarming and shows that not all methods are equally well able to estimate unbiased effects. Interestingly, the potentially best results in terms of deviations from the target value and standard errors are regression adjustment approaches, which apparently combine the best of both worlds. Users who want to stick to the linear regression model also have the option to transform their raw regression coefficients to the ATE using user-written commands such as `hettreatreg`. In any case, researchers should think about the potential presence of heterogeneous treatment effect and test for them explicitly.

Finally, several limitations of the simulation study should be noted. Many of the commands examined offer a wide range of options, giving users considerable flexibility to tailor methods to their specific research questions and data. At the same time, this flexibility implies that some commands require careful tuning, which may be challenging for less experienced analysts. For this reason, the present study relies primarily on default settings, with all deviations explicitly documented. Moreover, although the simulation settings were designed to resemble realistic empirical scenarios, real-world data can exhibit far greater complexity. Some methods may perform better in situations

13. <https://wordpress.its.virginia.edu/PolMeth/files/2013/07/Miller.pdf>

with extremely small samples or very large numbers of confounders. Accordingly, the results should be viewed as general guidance rather than a definitive ranking. Methods that perform poorly here may excel in other contexts. Finally, some of the commands considered support robust standard errors, while others (such as `kmatch`) do not. In some situations, robust standard errors may be unnecessary or even detrimental (King and Roberts 2015), whereas in others, more robust corrections may be required¹⁴—for example, `vce(hc3)`, which is available only for a limited set of estimation commands such as `regress`

5 Conclusion and recommendation

While statisticians and applied researchers often assume that complex and recently developed approaches for addressing confounding—such as matching or weighting methods—represent the most sophisticated tools for estimating unbiased treatment effects, our comprehensive simulation study provides only limited support for this view. Notably, the relatively simple linear (OLS) regression approach, which has been established for decades, frequently performs best in terms of bias, inference, and statistical power. In particular, when researchers are confident that all relevant confounders have been measured and that functional forms are correctly specified, `regress` outperforms all other methods considered. This advantage also persists in the presence of omitted variable bias. Regardless of how theoretically refined some methods may be, our practical evaluation offers little evidence that `regress` can be systematically outperformed in these settings. The main exception arises in situations involving model misspecification or when heterogeneous treatment effects are present. In such cases, certain matching and weighting approaches can yield smaller biases. However, these gains come at the cost of substantially larger standard errors, implying reduced precision and weaker inference. Researchers who are reluctant to use `regress` because they wish to report the ATE (or ATT) should note that linear regression coefficients can be easily transformed into ATEs. A convenient implementation of this transformation is provided by the user-written command `hettreatreg` (Słoczyński 2023), which also eliminates biases due to heterogeneous treatment effects.

Based on the empirical findings of this study, we offer the following recommendations. First, using `regress`—at least as an initial benchmark—is rarely a poor choice, as long treatment effect heterogeneity can be ruled out (which is quickly done by using a regression adjustment approach or by converting regression coefficients to ATEs). Applying multiple estimation commands is generally beneficial, as it provides insight into how sensitive results are to the choice of method. Second, when `regress` and alternative approaches such as entropy balancing or nearest-neighbor matching yield markedly different results, researchers should carefully reconsider the relationships among variables and assess the possibility of model misspecification. Recovering the correct functional form can substantially improve results without additional data collection or cost. A simple option is to conduct the Ramsey RESET-test with `estat ovtest` after `regress`,

14. <https://datacolada.org/99>

which can give a first indication of a model misspecification in the presence of nonlinear effects.

Third, users should be aware that many treatment-effect commands are useful not only for estimation but also for diagnostics. For example, the `teffects` commands do not produce estimates when the overlap assumption is violated; in such cases, users must manually exclude the flagged observations. Moreover, commands such as `kmatch summarize` and `tebalance summarize` allow researchers to assess whether treatment and control groups have been successfully balanced. If substantial differences between groups remain after matching or balancing, results should be interpreted with caution. In this respect, diagnostic checks are essential for evaluating whether balancing is feasible at all. If satisfactory balance cannot be achieved, estimates from `regress` are also likely to be biased. Finally, as our results demonstrate, incorrectly specified functional forms can introduce considerable bias. When it is difficult to derive all relevant functional relationships from theory—particularly when the number of confounders is large—data-driven approaches such as `lasso` may help identify relevant terms.¹⁵ Once selected, these variables can then be incorporated into any subsequent estimation command.

15. <https://blog.stata.com/2019/09/09/an-introduction-to-the-lasso-in-stata/>

6 Appendix

Table 2: Standardized simulation analysis

Method	reg	kmEb	kmEm	kmPs	kmMd	kmJpw	kmRa	aipw	ipw	ipwra	mmatch	psmatch	ra	t2_ipw
Unbiased setting														
Non-missing point estimates	96228	96228	64793	96228	96228	96217	96228	96224	96222	96228	96228	96228	96228	96166
Non-missing SEs	96228	96228	64793	96228	96228	96217	96228	96224	96222	96228	96228	96228	96228	96166
Bias in point estimate	0.001	0.001	-0.006	0.001	-0.430	0.050	0.001	0.001	-0.094	0.001	0.001	-0.033	0.001	0.001
Mean of point estimate	0.001	0.001	-0.006	0.001	-0.430	0.050	0.001	0.001	-0.094	0.001	0.001	-0.033	0.001	0.001
Empirical SE	0.066	0.082	0.100	0.083	0.495	0.116	0.070	0.082	0.155	0.082	0.094	0.124	0.070	0.087
% precision gain rel. to reg	0.000	-35.166	-56.735	-37.418	-98.239	-68.117	-12.283	-35.295	-82.067	-35.568	-50.710	-71.959	-12.283	-43.311
Mean squared error	0.004	0.007	0.010	0.007	0.429	0.016	0.005	0.007	0.033	0.007	0.009	0.016	0.005	0.008
Root mean squared error	0.066	0.082	0.100	0.083	0.655	0.127	0.070	0.082	0.181	0.082	0.094	0.128	0.070	0.087
RMS model-based SE	0.066	0.123	0.120	0.117	0.095	0.134	0.070	0.079	0.120	0.075	0.088	0.117	0.070	0.075
Mean CI width	0.237	0.424	0.408	0.408	0.337	0.447	0.250	0.277	0.387	0.270	0.311	0.393	0.249	0.269
Relative % error in SE	0.893	50.933	20.612	41.339	-80.838	15.288	0.172	-3.054	-22.846	-7.844	-6.313	-5.999	0.094	-13.791
% cov. of nonm. 95% CI	94.914	98.488	97.537	98.330	42.220	97.675	94.833	94.369	73.223	93.348	93.388	90.524	94.827	92.100
% power of 5% level test	5.086	1.512	2.463	1.670	57.780	2.325	5.167	5.631	26.777	6.652	6.612	9.476	5.173	7.900
Biased setting														
Non-missing point estimates	96228	96228	64950	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96219
Non-missing SEs	96228	96228	64950	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96228	96219
Bias in point estimate	-0.296	-0.309	-0.332	-0.308	-0.701	-0.261	-0.302	-0.316	-0.393	-0.317	-0.315	-0.345	-0.302	-0.319
Mean of point estimate	-0.296	-0.309	-0.332	-0.308	-0.701	-0.261	-0.302	-0.316	-0.393	-0.317	-0.315	-0.345	-0.302	-0.319
Empirical SE	0.204	0.217	0.326	0.217	0.377	0.239	0.210	0.220	0.233	0.220	0.225	0.234	0.210	0.223
% precision gain rel. to reg	0.000	-11.423	-60.682	-11.467	-70.608	-27.095	-5.408	-13.491	-23.086	-14.052	-17.109	-23.522	-5.408	-15.890
Mean squared error	0.129	0.142	0.216	0.142	0.633	0.126	0.135	0.148	0.209	0.149	0.149	0.174	0.135	0.151
Root mean squared error	0.359	0.377	0.465	0.377	0.796	0.354	0.368	0.385	0.457	0.386	0.387	0.417	0.368	0.389
RMS model-based SE	0.076	0.127	0.311	0.120	0.100	0.134	0.079	0.086	0.117	0.083	0.094	0.120	0.079	0.083
Mean CI width	0.269	0.441	0.930	0.423	0.357	0.457	0.278	0.304	0.391	0.297	0.334	0.411	0.278	0.296
Relative % error in SE	-62.828	-41.463	-4.481	-44.567	-73.429	-43.848	-62.603	-60.665	-49.898	-62.232	-58.040	-48.611	-62.632	-62.805
% cov. of nonm. 95% CI	23.379	38.342	52.238	36.842	6.923	44.303	23.732	24.490	19.885	23.777	27.421	28.924	23.728	23.437
% power of 5% level test	76.621	61.658	47.762	63.158	93.077	55.697	76.268	75.510	80.115	76.223	72.579	71.076	76.272	76.563
Incorrect functional form														
Non-missing point estimates	95930	95930	64792	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	94497
Non-missing SEs	95930	95930	64792	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	95930	94497
Bias in point estimate	-0.347	-0.016	-0.012	-0.267	-0.645	-0.324	-0.442	-0.519	-0.567	-0.468	-0.202	-0.375	-0.442	-0.419
Mean of point estimate	-0.347	-0.016	-0.012	-0.267	-0.645	-0.324	-0.442	-0.519	-0.567	-0.468	-0.202	-0.375	-0.442	-0.419
Empirical SE	0.227	0.154	0.110	0.298	0.618	0.291	0.273	0.333	0.333	0.295	0.200	0.338	0.273	0.271
% precision gain rel. to reg	0.000	117.957	323.138	-42.263	-86.571	-39.367	-31.115	-53.805	-53.703	-41.156	28.327	-54.921	-31.115	-30.259
Mean squared error	0.172	0.024	0.012	0.160	0.799	0.190	0.270	0.380	0.432	0.306	0.081	0.255	0.270	0.249
Root mean squared error	0.414	0.154	0.111	0.401	0.894	0.435	0.519	0.617	0.657	0.554	0.285	0.505	0.519	0.499
RMS model-based SE	0.094	0.176	0.132	0.130	0.107	0.137	0.093	0.125	0.131	0.100	0.116	0.160	0.093	0.096
Mean CI width	0.330	0.609	0.461	0.454	0.385	0.454	0.327	0.414	0.429	0.356	0.410	0.534	0.327	0.341
Relative % error in SE	-58.371	14.845	20.123	-56.416	-82.660	-52.849	-66.058	-62.374	-60.594	-66.049	-42.028	-52.733	-66.084	-64.589
% cov. of nonm. 95% CI	22.380	95.806	97.202	54.585	31.084	38.123	16.778	16.281	14.281	16.979	50.753	41.767	16.766	18.730
% power of 5% level test	77.611	4.194	2.798	45.415	68.916	61.877	83.222	83.719	85.719	83.021	49.247	58.233	83.234	81.270
Heterog. treatment effects														
Non-missing point estimates	96228	96228	64798	96228	96228	96217	96228	96225	96224	96228	96228	96227	96228	96162
Non-missing SEs	96228	96228	64798	96228	96228	96217	96228	96225	96224	96228	96228	96227	96228	96162
Bias in point estimate	-0.091	-0.016	-0.055	-0.015	-0.488	0.042	0.000	0.000	-0.112	0.000	0.000	-0.039	0.000	0.000
Mean of point estimate	-0.091	-0.016	-0.055	-0.015	-0.488	0.042	0.000	0.000	-0.112	0.000	0.000	-0.039	0.000	0.000
Empirical SE	0.126	0.087	0.122	0.091	0.528	0.128	0.071	0.082	0.174	0.082	0.094	0.135	0.071	0.087
% precision gain rel. to reg	0.000	108.836	6.663	90.259	-94.343	-3.517	210.081	132.915	-48.050	132.631	79.944	-13.632	210.081	106.881
Mean squared error	0.024	0.008	0.018	0.009	0.517	0.018	0.005	0.007	0.043	0.007	0.009	0.020	0.005	0.008
Root mean squared error	0.155	0.088	0.133	0.092	0.719	0.134	0.071	0.082	0.207	0.082	0.094	0.141	0.071	0.087
RMS model-based SE	0.069	0.141	0.136	0.134	0.108	0.154	0.072	0.081	0.135	0.077	0.092	0.126	0.072	0.077
Mean CI width	0.246	0.486	0.466	0.465	0.382	0.514	0.257	0.285	0.435	0.277	0.325	0.420	0.272	0.277
Relative % error in SE	-45.054	61.938	12.191	46.896	-79.520	20.205	1.569	-1.485	-22.356	-5.958	-1.963	-6.435	1.490	-11.568
% cov. of nonm. 95% CI	63.729	98.772	94.018	98.470	39.601	98.090	95.341	94.791	71.115	93.803	94.387	90.232	95.337	92.619
% power of 5% level test	36.271	1.228	5.982	1.530	60.399	1.910	4.659	5.209	28.885	6.197	5.613	9.768	4.663	7.381

Table notes: table created using the user-written command `simsum` (White 2010). Note that the results do not necessarily agree with the results presented in the main text, as `simsum` computes the bias as the difference between the coefficient and the target, while in the main text, the absolute difference is used. For the exact formulas used, refer to the journal article. The results for `kmatch em` are not trustworthy, as this command did not produce any result quite often.

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